

ON THE POSSIBLE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CAROTENE, VITAMIN-C, TOTAL ACIDITY, pH AND SUGAR CONTENT OF DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF MANGOES DURING THEIR GREEN AND RIPE CONDITIONS

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Several varieties of mangoes have been examined in their unripe, partly ripe and fully ripe conditions for their carotene, vitamin-C and sugar content and for their total acidity and pH values.

This investigation was undertaken with a view to finding out (i) the nutritive values of different varieties of mangoes (available in Calcutta) with regard to their carotene, vitamin-C, and sugar content, and their total acidity and pH , (ii) variations in these values during their green and ripe conditions, and (iii) whether any relationship exists between (a) the progressive diminution of vitamin-C and of total acidity or the gradual rise in pH , or (b) between the increase in carotene and that of sugar, and (c) between the decrease of vitamin-C or of total acidity on the one hand and the increase of carotene or sugar on the other. To carry out this investigation properly in the case of each variety of mango, it is necessary to get hold of green mangoes of a particular variety from the same tree,* to analyse some of them for these constituents, to ripen others in the laboratory in a thermostat and to analyse these ripe mangoes again for the same constituents. As it was not possible to know whether mangoes of a particular variety, packed up in a basket, belonged to the same tree or not, care was taken to select green and ripe mangoes which appeared to be of the same general appearance from the same basket. These were then analysed. In some cases green mangoes were ripened in the laboratory and then analysed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation of Total Acidity, pH , and Sugar.—A weighed amount of the pulp of the mango under examination was triturated with sand and distilled water and the extract so obtained was decanted off into a 250 c.c. measuring flask. This process was repeated till complete extraction. The total extracts were collected in the flask and made up to a known volume with distilled water.

Aliquot portions of this liquid were used for the determination of sugar by the micro-Benedict method, of pH with the Coles' potentiometer, while the remaining portion was titrated directly with a $N/10$ Na_2CO_3 solution for total acidity.

Estimation of Vitamin-C.—Vitamin-C was extracted from a weighed amount of the sample by thoroughly macerating with a mixture of HCl (4%) and metaphosphoric acid (2%) and sand. It was then estimated as usual by titration of the extract with Tillman's dye before and after its aliquot portions were treated with hex-oxidase (ascorbic acid oxidase), prepared from drumstick juice (Srinivasan, *Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 1524).

It is well known that mangoes of the same denomination differ widely in taste and therefore in chemical composition not only when they belong to different places but also amongst different gardens of the same locality.

Estimation of Carotene.—The weighed sample of the mango pulp was thoroughly ground with glass powder and extracted with absolute alcohol several times and the extract was then kept in a stoppered cylinder or preferably in a separating funnel. The pulp was then extracted with petroleum ether for 4 to 5 times till the pulp was colourless. Both the alcoholic and ethereal extracts were

TABLE I

No. of samples.	Variety of mango.	* Carotene (I. U.)	† Vitamin-C.	Total acidity:	pH.	Sugar**
<i>Langra</i>						
1.	(unripe)	11.6	220.4	19.0 c.c.	4.2	2.2
2.	(another sample)			42.0	3.11	1.15
3.	(partly ripe)	18.8	120.0	17.0	4.2	1.34
4.	(ripe)	60.0	60.0	7.25	5.19	2.0
<i>Fazli</i>						
1.	(partly ripe)	9.6	24.0	13.0	4.13	1.68
2.	(ripe)	45.2	20.8	8.25	4.33	2.5
3.	(Benares variety, unripe)	4.0	17.6	20.0	3.76	2.6
4.	.. (ripe)	31.5	12.8	10.0	4.36	2.7
<i>Totafully</i>						
1.	(partly ripe)	16.0	24.0	23.0	3.57	2.5
2.	(ripe)	24.6	16.0	13.0	4.1	4.0
<i>Bombai</i>						
1.	(partly ripe)	16.4	18.0	11.5	4.0	3.0
2.	(ripe)	54.4	6.4	8.0	4.63	3.39
<i>Kishanvog</i>						
1.	(green)	7.2	28.8	20.0	3.8	2.56
2.	(ripe)	42.4	17.6	6.5	4.63	3.12
<i>Taraiha</i>						
1.	(unripe)	2.8	36.0	24.24	3.29	2.22
2.	(ripe)	14.8	22.0	10.5	4.33	2.5
<i>Sepia</i>						
1.	(unripe)	6.5	14.4	22.5	3.78	2.8
2.	(partly ripe)	11.5	12.0	31.5	3.66	2.8
3.	(ripe)	25.5	9.6	23.0	4.06	3.9
4.	(ripe)	45.0	9.6	18.5	4.1	4.2

mixed up in the separating funnel (graduated) and then allowed to separate, and a measured volume of water was added to make the alcoholic layer about 85%. The mixture was then thoroughly shaken in the separating funnel and the alcoholic layer was thrown out after again allowing the two layers to separate. The petroleum

* The carotene figures (per 100 g. of mango pulp) are expressed as microgrammes of mixed carotene.

1 microgramme is considered to represent roughly 1 International unit (I. U.) of vitamin-A.

† Expressed in mg. per 100 g. pulp.

‡ per 100 g. pulp equivalent to *N*-acid.

** Expressed as g. per 100 g. of pulp.

ether layer containing the carotene was washed successively with 85% and 70% alcohol and repeatedly with water. The moisture in the ethereal layer was then removed by anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and shaken with sufficient powdered dry CaCO_3 to remove chlorophylls and possible traces of non-hydrocarbon pigments. The ethereal solution was next filtered and the filtrate was made up to a suitable volume. The carotene content of the extract was estimated colorimetrically by matching against a standard solution of pure β -carotene.

The results of analysis of several samples of mangoes are given in Table I.

C O N C L U S I O N S

On examining these results of analysis the following conclusions are drawn :

(a) The unripe mangoes are, as was expected, more acid and richer in vitamin-C than ripe mangoes.

(c) Ripe mangoes are richer in carotene and sugar than unripe ones.

(c) The increase in carotene content of mangoes on ripening is generally proportionately much greater than the decrease in their vitamin-C or acid content and bears no relation to the sugar content of these mangoes. (In the case of Totafully and Bombai, the increase in carotene is closely similar to the decrease in vitamin-C on ripening).

(d) No proportional relationship exists between the vitamin-C content of a mango and its acidity or between the decrease of acidity and the increase of sugar content of a mango on ripening.

(e) With the same or nearly the same p_{H} , different acid contents are found in different mangoes and also no proportional relationship exists in many cases between its acid content and p_{H} , indicating that the organic acid salt content of these mangoes varies widely, i.e., their potentially acid or basic character is different with different mangoes.

(f) Ripe *Langras* are richer in both carotene and vitamin-C than other mangoes.

(g) The ripe *Bombai* mangoes, *Fazli*, *Sepia* and *Kishenvog* are also fairly rich in carotene.

(h) The vitamin-C content of unripe *langras* is much greater than that of other mangoes.

(i) The sugar content of ripe *Sepia*, *Totafully* and *Bombai* is appreciably higher than that of other mangoes,

(j) The acid content of ripe *Kishenvog* is the least and that of ripe *Langra*, *Bombai*, *Fazli* and *Taraiha* is also quite small in comparison with other mangoes.